

conditions, the three varieties yielded similarly. The participating farmers were generally satisfied with the performance of the new varieties. OHV has undertaken seed multiplication of all three varieties. □

Ranbir Basmati — an early-maturing aromatic rice

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The quality basmati rices of India and Pakistan, characterized by late maturity, are difficult to fit into multiple farming systems, and are grown on limited hectareage. Development of early-maturing basmati types would help bring larger areas under superfine rices.

In 1982, we isolated an early-maturing, slightly dwarf plant from farmers' fields. The strain, Ranbir Basmati, was evaluated against Basmati 370 for 2 yr at RARS, and in farmers' fields for performance, stability, and adaptability. Ranbir Basmati duration is 115-120 d from sowing to maturity, 30-35 d shorter than that of Basmati 370, with comparable yields. Yield per day of Ranbir Basmati was 20-25% higher. Grain quality equaled or surpassed that of Basmati 370 (see table). □

Comparative qualities of Ranbir Basmati and Basmati 370.

Character	Ranbir Basmati	Basmati 370
Plant height (cm)	155	170
Duration (d)	115	150
Threshability	Easy	Easy
Grain length (mm)	7.2	7.1
Grain breadth (mm)	1.8	1.9
Length/breadth ratio	3.9	3.8
Chalkiness	5	9
1,000-grain wt (g)	22.8	21.5
Amylose content (%)	24.0	21.3
Gelatinization temperature ^a	I/L	H/I
Average proportional elongation ratio	2.05	2.03
Protein content (%)	7.7	7.0
Aroma	Strong	Strong
Cooking quality	Good	Good
Eating quality	Good	Good

^a L = low, H = high, I = intermediate.

RAU4045-10, a new variety for rainfed areas

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RAU4045-10 (IET7978), a semidwarf variety derived from Finegora/ IET2832, is moderately resistant to blast and averages 70 d to 50% flowering. Mean yield over 4 yr of experimental trials was 3.6 t/ha, significantly higher than that of check varieties Akashi (2.3 t/ha) and Brown gora (2.1 t/ha).

IET7978 was tested for 3 yr in All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement

Project (AICRIP) experiments. In the 1984 Preliminary Varietal Trial 1 (PVT-1), it yielded 5.5 t/ha at Hyderabad. In the 1985 Uniform Varietal Trial in 15 locations all over India, it yielded an average 2.6 t/ha and took 74 d to flowering under direct seeded rainfed conditions (Table 1) and 3.7 t/ha under direct seeded irrigated conditions. It ranked third in transplanted conditions in 16 locations.

In 1986, IET7978 was the top yielder (3 t/ha) over all locations (Table 2). It significantly outyielded national as well as local checks under rainfed conditions in Bihar and Orissa and has been recommended for rainfed fields in Bihar and Orissa. □

Table 1. Performance of RAU4045-10 in station trials at Birsa Agricultural University, Kanke, Ranchi, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				
	1983	1984	1985	1986	Mean
RAU4045-10 (IET7978)	4.2	3.8	3.0	3.4	3.6
Akashi	2.5	2.4	2.1	2.4	2.3
Brown gora	1.9	2.0	2.2	2.3	2.1
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.4

Table 2. Performance of RAU4045-10 in All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project trials during 1986.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)								
	Zone III		Zone 5		Mean	Zone 8		Transplanting condition	
	Assam	Assam and Tripura	Kanke Bihar	Faizabad (U.P.)		Himachal Pradesh	Tamil Nadu	Delhi	Rajasthan
RAU4045-10	2.6	3.1	4.1	4.1	3.1	3.7	5.0	5.9	3.0
Akashi	2.1	3.0	3.2	4.4	2.9	2.1	4.0	3.4	2.4
Cauvery	1.4	2.2	2.4	3.2	2.3	1.8	4.5	4.8	2.9
Local checks	—	—	2.2	3.6	—	2.8	4.7	—	—
				(N22)		(HPU741)	(IR50)		

CN705-18 — a promising rice variety for deepwater rice areas

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Based on overall performance in 1985-87 national trials, CN705-18 (IET9065 =

Mahsuril CN643) is a promising variety for deepwater rice areas (water accumulates up to 1 m during the wet season) in West Bengal, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh, and Assam.

Photoperiod-sensitive CN705-18 flowered 28-30 Oct in West Bengal. Depending on water depth, it attained 175-210 cm height, with 10-12 tillers/hill. It has very good submergence